

Horizon Europe Project PLANET4B

FINAL COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION (CDE) STRATEGY

BETTER DECISIONS FOR BIODIVERSITY AND PEOPLE

PLANET4B

Funded by
the European Union

PLANET4B receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101082212.

UK Research
and Innovation

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

Views and opinions are of those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, European Commission, the government of the United Kingdom, or the government of Switzerland. The European Union, the European Commission, the government of the United Kingdom, or the government of Switzerland cannot be held responsible for them.

PLANET4B

BETTER DECISIONS FOR BIODIVERSITY AND PEOPLE

Key deliverable information

Project acronym **PLANET4B**

Project title	understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making
Starting date	01 st November 2022
Duration	36 months
Website	https://planet4b.eu/
Project coordination and scientific lead team	Ilkhom Soliev; Alex Franklin; Agnes Zolyomi; Torsten Wähler

Deliverable number **D5.3**

Deliverable title	Final communication, dissemination and exploitation (CDE) strategy (version 3.0)
Task leader	GoodIssue nonprofit Ltd. (GD)
Corresponding author	Gyula Tóth
Dissemination level	Public
Status	Final

Deliverable description

Final communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy of the Horizon Europe PLANET4B project including updates of the strategy and setting out activities for four years after the end of the project.

Version	Status	Date	Authors/Reviewers
0.1	Draft	23/09/2025	Authors: Gyula Tóth (GD); Zsuzsanna Király (GD); Mária Csikai (GD)
0.2	Draft	26/09/2025	Reviewers: Agnes Zolyomi (MLU) Lindy Binder (CU)
0.3	Draft	02/10/2025	Authors: Gyula Tóth (GD); Zsuzsanna Király (GD); Mária Csikai (GD)
1.0	Final	27/10/2025	Reviewer: Torsten Wähler

Recommended citation

Tóth, G, Király, Z., & Csikai, M. (2025). Final communication, dissemination and exploitation (CDE) strategy (version 3.0). Report No. D5.3 of the Horizon Europe Project 101082212 – PLANET4B. Brussels. European Research Executive Agency. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17243193

Rights and license

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The Creative Commons Attribution license allows re-distribution and re-use of a licensed work on the condition that the creator is appropriately credited. [Read more](#).

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Definition
CAC	The Climate Academy
CBD	Convention of Biological Diversity
CDE	Communication Dissemination and Exploitation
CG	CzechGlobe – Global Change Research Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences
CGE	Culture Goes Europe
COMCOM	Communication Committee of the project
CU	Coventry University
D	Deliverable
DC	Dadima's CIC
EO	Expected Outcome
ESSRG	Environmental Social Science Research Group
FiBL	Research Institute of Organic Agriculture
FUG	Forum Urban Gardening
GA	Grant Agreement Project 101082212 – PLANET4B
GD	GoodIssue nonprofit Ltd.
HRP	Horizon Results Platform
IFZ	Interdisciplinary Research Centre for Technology, Work and Culture
IPBES	Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month (of the project time)
MLU	Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg
NINA	Norwegian Institute for Nature Research
OOF	Greater Oslo Council for Outdoor Recreation
PCT	Project Coordination Team
PLANET4B	understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making
PP	Project Partner
RU	Radboud University

TG1-6	Target group 1-6
TEHRA	The Environment and Human Rights Academy
UNEP-WCMC	UN Environment Programme World Conservation Monitoring Centre
UNIFI	University of Pisa
WP	Work Package

Table of contents

Key deliverable information	iii
List of abbreviations and acronyms	v
1. Executive summary	3
2. About the PLANET4B project	4
3. The Communication Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) Strategy	5
3.1 Introduction	5
3.2 Defining communication, dissemination and exploitation	6
3.3 Objectives	6
3.4 Strategy and planning	7
3.5 Summary of the achievements	7
4. Target audience and messages	8
4.1 General messages of the project	8
4.2 Policymakers	10
4.3 Businesses	12
4.4 Civil society	13
4.5 Scientific community, researchers	15
4.6 Youth, educators and social movements	16
4.7 Local communities	17
4.8 General public	17
5. Communication and Dissemination Plan	19
5.1 Phases of communication	19
5.2 Project Partner's responsibilities and workflow	20
6. Communication channels and tools	21
6.1 Visual identity	21
6.2 Written contents	22
6.3 Website	22
6.4 Social media channels	24
6.5 Newsletter	28
6.6 Briefs	29
6.7 Press releases	29
6.8 Scientific and non-scientific publications	29
6.9 Emails	30
6.10 Open-source platforms	30
6.11 Events	30
6.12 Consultations	30
6.13 Other visual tools	31

6.14 Media relations	31
7. Synergies and accelerating changes	31
7.1 The Synergies Strategy	31
7.2 Channelling outcomes to accelerate change	31
8. Capacity building for enabling players	32
9. Internal communication.....	32
10. Exploitation and dissemination	33
10.1. Introduction & summary.....	33
10.2. Identification of Key Exploitable Results (KERs).....	34
10.3. Insight into the exploitation plan of each Key Exploitable Results (KER) in the PLANET4B project	36
10.4 Additional dissemination and exploitation activities.....	46
11. Monitoring results.....	48

1. Executive summary

This document serves as the final version of Deliverable 5.1 (D5.1) – the “Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CDE) strategy” of Work Package 5 in the PLANET4B project.

The document is based on the content of the first and the mid-term versions of the CDE Strategy, which reviews the communication and dissemination tools, methods, and strategies applied during the project. The current version of the document reflects the situation as of September 2025 with relevant updates.

The updated chapter 10 “Exploitation and Dissemination” explains in detail the activities the consortium will undertake after the project closing to ensure its results are put to use. It defines the Key Exploitable Results and how these will be shared with target groups, as well as the additional dissemination efforts partners will carry out to make sure the project’s research outcomes and key findings reach a broader audience and provide a foundation for further research, policy-making, and new projects.

Chapter 10 was developed with the support and guidance of the Horizon Results Booster (<https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>), whose assistance is gratefully acknowledged.

2. About the PLANET4B project

We rely on biodiversity for our very existence – it provides us with the basic ecosystem services that allow us to survive and thrive. Still, human lives and the biosphere itself are under threat due to the loss of biodiversity occurring at a massive scale, and at an accelerating pace. Despite the mounting scientific evidence on the importance of biodiversity, it still takes a back seat to political and other agendas.

How can we change this alarming situation? The PLANET4B (understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making) research project aims to understand and influence decision making affecting biodiversity. The project's main objectives are: 1) to understand how factors such as gender, religion, ethnicity, race, age, culture, disability, norms, values and behaviour intersect and are implicated in biodiversity relevant decision making across a range of different scales and settings; and 2) to channel this understanding of complexity into the design of stakeholder interventions, transformative pathways and a series of targeted, yet scalable policy recommendations in order to prioritise biodiversity and halt biodiversity loss.

3. The Communication Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) Strategy

3.1 Introduction

The final version of CDE Strategy is informed by our experiences and achievements during the project, including our communication activities, internal meetings, and valuable feedback from our project partners.

The process of creating the final CDE Strategy involved retaining majority of the original content, reflecting its ongoing relevance.

The updates aim to effectively communicate the adjustments made in the plan, highlighting the continuity from the original strategy while incorporating new insights and strategies.

There are two major communication challenges the project faces. Probably the most significant one is that the communication sphere is overcrowded. The project's target audience are constantly overwhelmed with information. The other challenge is that PLANET4B is a (technical) research project but one of its main aims is to influence decision-makers (to generate transformative change), who are often hard to reach. Both challenges can be addressed in several ways to have more significant impact, or more engagement with decision-makers.

To stand out and optimise the impact of PLANET4B – with the help of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) Strategy – the project has developed clear, understandable, targeted and co-created messages to the target groups, while also presenting key results in both structurally and visually engaging ways. The main objective of the communication activities has been to increase the visibility of the project and its results ensuring that the scientific work is effectively communicated. The communication activities go beyond reaching and engaging with the key target groups (policymakers, businesses, civil society, scientific community, youth and educators), and also focus on local communities and stakeholders of the project's case studies, and on the general public.

Central to the communication activities is content creation, which is built on the close cooperation among the project partners (PPs). These contents are related to e.g. how we perceive biodiversity, what research results are there on how we make relevant decision-making or how local stakeholders can build transformative pathways. As one of the central aspects of the project is to understand how intersectional characteristics define decision-making, careful consideration of different cultural and social contexts has been made during the project's communication and dissemination activities.

3.2 Defining communication, dissemination and exploitation

Using the European Commission's definition¹ (in relation to Horizon Europe projects): communication is “reaching out to society and showing the impact and benefits of EU-funded activities”, whereas communication activities, within the frame of EU projects are to “inform about and promote the project and its results, success in a non-technical manner.” Dissemination, on the other hand, focuses on the public disclosure of results, enabling others (policymakers, researchers, etc.) to use or re-use or internalise results and thus maximise the impact of EU-funded research.

However, communication and dissemination activities are intertwined and therefore cannot always be clearly distinguished from each other. “The boundaries between certain activities – in particular regarding communication actions and dissemination – are often blurry or can sometimes overlap. For instance, a magazine article highlighting the project's work and achievements that is written for communication purposes could end up in the hands of potential stakeholders outside the project and trigger interest in using some of the results. The initial communication activity has now become a dissemination tool as well.”²

Exploitation means the use of results in developing, creating and marketing or improving a product or process, or in creating and providing a service in standardisation activities or shaping a policy.³

3.3 Objectives

The main purpose of this document is to provide a clear definition and explanation of the various communication instruments as well as the target audience and strategies in formulating messages. This helps PPs communicate more effectively and ensure that their efforts are aligned with achieving the project goals. Additionally, the CDE strategy and the annual CDE plan clearly outline the roles and responsibilities of each partner in executing different communication and dissemination activities. By establishing clear accountability, the plan aims to optimise communication efforts and maximise their impact on the intended audience. The CDE strategy and plan also ensures that relevant actions address the key target groups with tailored messages through the relevant channels and in the most appropriate formats.

The overarching goal of the communication and dissemination activities is to initiate, accelerate and upscale biodiversity-relevant transformative changes in our society by disseminating the project results to researchers, scientific and policymaking institutions

¹ For all citations in this chapter see European IT Helpdesk (2022) as the relevant reference: European Commission, European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency, Scherer, J., Weber, S., Alveen, P., et al. (2022). European IP Helpdesk. Successful valorisation of knowledge and research results in Horizon Europe. Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation. Ingbert, Publications Office of the European Union. Available from: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2826/437645>. Access: April 24th, 2023.

² For all citations in this chapter see European IT Helpdesk (2022) as the relevant reference: European Commission, European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency, Scherer, J., Weber, S., Alveen, P., et al. (2022). European IP Helpdesk. Successful valorisation of knowledge and research results in Horizon Europe. Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation. Ingbert, Publications Office of the European Union. Available from: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2826/437645>. Access: April 24th, 2023.

³ https://rea.ec.europa.eu/dissemination-and-exploitation_en

and networks, the related target groups and the general public. In addition, these activities aim to increase the visibility of the project and its results, ensuring that the scientific work is effectively communicated (and to understand how to communicate biodiversity more effectively). The activities defined in the plan are designed to raise awareness and maximise the impact of the project outputs.

We have also been committed to a regular monitoring and revision process, occurring every six months until the final monitoring and reporting phase of the project, to ensure our strategy remains effective and responsive to the evolving needs of the project. This continual refinement process allowed us to adapt our approach effectively and align it with the progress and learnings from the project.

3.4 Strategy and planning

This CDE strategy was designed to help the PPs communicate effectively to achieve the project's objectives. This document defines the strategy's objectives (why we want to do it), the target audience (for whom), the messages (what we want to say), the channels (how we want to say it) and the actions (what we want to do). In other words: the CDE strategy aims to identify who needs to be reached and in what way, and when the target groups need to be addressed to successfully achieve a more substantial impact.

This Communication and Dissemination strategy has worked as a detailed roadmap to organise the communication work according to timeline, needs and resources. While the strategy focuses on "what to do", the plan instructs "how to do it" providing guidance on how to implement the strategy. The plan is specific, time-bound, and is developed regularly.

3.5 Summary of the achievements

During the lifetime of the PLANET4B project, we have witnessed significant progress alongside various challenges in our communication and dissemination endeavours. Our experience shows that our activities have successfully attracted attention with notable achievements like number of website visitors, and social media engagement demonstrating encouraging growth. We have identified challenges in maximising engagement and effectively disseminating information to our diverse target groups. These insights have been instrumental in shaping the updates to our final Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Strategy, guiding us to focus on enhanced partner involvement, innovative content creation, and broader dissemination strategies for the project's crucial final phase.

In terms of concrete achievements and measurable outcomes, we have successfully met, and in some cases surpassed our initial targets. Exceeding the initial targets, the project was already presented at 60+ scientific events by the project partners and published 40+ non-scientific articles at the PLANET4B website, partners' websites, and external media, e.g. wmn.hu, maghaz.hu, queers.com, nfz.ch, alterclimatechange.com, etc. The partnership published 20+ videos (and many more will be available at the Care-Full Courses and Resources platform – D5.9), which exceeded the objective of creating 10 videos throughout the entire project.

26 consultations have been held with EU and local policymakers, business actors, experts and networks in education in order to support strategy planning or provide information about the research and findings of PLANET4B, e.g., City of Graz, Convention on Biological Diversity, Natural Environment Research Council, Welsh Parliament Climate Change, Environment and Infrastructure Committee, UNEP Brussels, UNEP Global Environment Outlook 7, UN Women, UNDP, PROTEUS partnership, Joint Research Centre, Climate Policy Forum, GreenComp, Volens Association (NGO in Romania), Education for Climate Community Café, schools, Shared Green Deal and other Horizon Europe projects.

The consortium also successfully organised a final conference in Brussels to present the project results to a wider audience, while through our regular social media presence, we achieved around 800 posts and more than 1,100 followers.

4. Target audience and messages

4.1 General messages of the project

In respect of interacting with the target audience and motivating it to act, clearly defined messages have been crucial. Messages articulate and encapsulate what the project is about, but more importantly why it is vital and relevant for the target groups. Messages should convey responses to: Why should they be interested in the project/results? How could they benefit from the results of the project? What do we offer to them? What do we want them to do?

Relevant messages can (and should) be used in every project activity, whether a partner is posting on social media, presenting at a conference, writing the summary of a report or talking to a journalist. Messages can help partners to improve communication, to influence decision making and to achieve impact.

The following table (Table 1) includes examples for general messages, relating to the topics of the project, to aspects of credibility (e.g. to gain trust) as well as to aspects of novelty of the project’s work.

Table 1. Main general messages of the project. Source: Authors’ own work.

Category	Message
Topic-related (biodiversity, decision making, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity loss threatens our existence. Yet, this crisis is only getting worse showing inapt governance. • Our current socio-economic system built on consumption and overexploitation stands against nature and biodiversity (and us). • To affectively address this system and trigger transformation, we need to better understand why biodiversity is not prioritised at the first place. • Within PLANET4B, we investigate why we do not already prioritise biodiversity and nature although we all find it important. • We assess governing norms, values and belief systems as well as intersectionality aspects (e.g. gender, age, race, religion).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We use transdisciplinary research and practices from economy through conservation to arts to analyse how we can make biodiversity more of a priority at the individual, community and institutional level. • We provide practical guidance for policymakers, civil society members and businesses about how they can change minds and make better decisions for biodiversity saving the planet. • We assess how religion, age, gender, disability and race may influence decision making on prioritising biodiversity through 11 case studies from eight countries. • We assess how various sectors (education, fashion industry, finance, agriculture, trade) can reduce individual and institutional barriers to upscale biodiversity decision making. • We attempt to understand how the locally gained knowledge can be built into the global level influencing major policies. • We bridge a knowledge gap about understanding how biodiversity can be prioritised in individual and policy decision making. • The PLANET4B project deals with the globally relevant topic of biodiversity loss that affects all humankind and has consequences for our future and survival (keywords: our existence, crucial, survival, alarming, biodiversity loss, etc.). • The project tries to understand how we can make decision making prioritise biodiversity more. • The project supports transformative actions for biodiversity.
Credibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The PLANET4B project is a cooperation between 16 partners from 10 countries: renowned universities, NGOs and SMEs, from all around Europe. • More than 60 researchers and experts are working on the outcomes.
Novelty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PLANET4B performs unique research on the topic. • Thanks to the consortium's wide transdisciplinary composition, the project can integrate knowledge from different disciplines (including political sciences, economics, sociology, psychology and communication sciences) as well as build on policy and practical knowledge. • The project compiles a much-needed gap-filling knowledge resource. • The project's research process is transdisciplinary, creative, action-oriented and participatory. • The findings are synthesised and scaled up to EU and global levels. • The project hopes to trigger transformative change so biodiversity can be prioritised in decision making.

The target groups of the project are:

- Policymakers
- Businesses
- Civil society
- Scientific community
- Local communities
- Youth, educators and social movements
- General public

Before dissemination activities could be realised, certain questions needed to be clarified to better understand and address the specific target group: What do we know about them? (What are their needs, news/information consuming habits?) What do we want to say/offer to them? How can we help them? What do we want them to do? What is their role in the solution?

4.2 Policymakers

One of the most influential actors to trigger transformative change may be relevant policymakers. To prioritise biodiversity and halt biodiversity loss, the co-produced knowledge of the project is channelled into targeted, yet scalable policy recommendations. The project participants ensure that the co-produced knowledge reaches the policymakers at the public and private levels, and that relevant knowledge is considered in policymaking. As a result of the dissemination, policymakers will understand better the importance of biodiversity, their role in transformation changes, the integration option of biodiversity to policy, the various factors defining decision making and the relevant institutional barriers and enablers. They will be able to make more effective biodiversity policy implementation, better policy formulation and prioritisation of biodiversity as well as better consideration of biodiversity in implementation. In addition, they will not only have a better understanding of the reviews and evaluation of policies but also integrate biodiversity into sectoral policy transitions. Furthermore, the dissemination of results will ensure policy coherence with international processes and aid plausible policy transitions.

The policymakers have been reached mainly through bilateral policy consultations and policy events as well as via the project’s social media channels, using news, posts, briefs, illustrated transitional stories and policy reports. Also, three workshops with relevant EU and national policymakers (e.g. DG RTD, Natural Environment Research Council, UK, JRC) have been realised. These workshops and consultations have been held in-person in Brussels, at relevant international events or online organised by the PPs. The workshops were built on (and integrate the results of) the specific case studies from WP3. Sectoral specific policy recommendations (agriculture, trade, finance, industry, education) about how transition can be upscaled to the EU and global levels have been communicated through targeted dissemination addressing key enablers. Collaborating with relevant UN bodies (e.g. UNEP, UN Women) will further ensure relevant messages are received by target groups and policy processes. The recommendations for EU and international policies (about how behavioural and intersectionality insights can aid policy coherence and implementation and how biodiversity can be further prioritised) are targeting to reach 100 enabling players using a synthesis policy report.

The following table (Table 2) includes specific messages for policymakers, listing their relevant outcomes, timeframe for realisation, channels and tools.

Table 2. Specific messages for policymakers Source: Authors’ own work.

Category	Message
What do we offer them?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Using the PLANET4B outcomes policymakers can communicate better about biodiversity issues.

<p>Why should they be interested in the project/results?</p> <p>How could they benefit from the results of the project?</p> <p>What do we want them to do?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policymakers can make more effective policy formulation and implementation in relation to biodiversity. • Policymakers can integrate biodiversity consideration in policymaking. • The project results provide a deeper understanding of the motivation behind business, institutional and private decision making that helps to implement existing biodiversity related policies more effectively. • The project can aid understanding how policies can best have a positive impact on biodiversity. • The project reveals major causes of limited biodiversity prioritisation and provides enablers for transformative change to limit and ultimately, stop biodiversity change. • The project promotes biodiversity and nature-based solutions that contribute to the food, water and raw materials security. • Policymakers can find the field of cooperation with businesses, education, the scientific sector and civil society working on biodiversity topics from local to global levels.
<p>Relevant outcomes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D4.1 – Entry points for upscaling findings at relevant scales identified, based on consultations with key enabling players (EU policymakers and businesses). • D4.2 – Mapping of leverage points and transformative pathways for upscaling at the EU as well as global context, produced for five sectors (agriculture, finance, education, industry, trade). • D4.3 – Reports from workshops on validated methods and pathways at EU, global and sector level. • D4.4 – Knowledge products, including synthesis of the applicability of behaviour science and intersectionality for prioritising biodiversity into relevant EU and global processes. • D5.8 – Three comprehensive guidelines tailored for enabling players (civil society, policymakers and businesses).
<p>Timeframe</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuously, during the project • Intensive dissemination: M28–M36
<p>Channels</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshops • Meetings, bilateral consultations • Social media (LinkedIn, Twitter) • Newsletter • Conferences, events
<p>Tools</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy report • Presentations • Briefs • Infographics • Illustrated transformative change stories

4.3 Businesses

Business decisions are crucial in preventing biodiversity loss as companies have a direct impact on the environment through their operations and supply chains. They can also influence consumer behaviour and policies through their actions and advocacy. To stop biodiversity loss, businesses can adopt sustainable sourcing, energy efficiency, corporate responsibility practices that prioritise sustainability and biodiversity, and advocate for policies that support conservation and sustainability. Overall, businesses have the power to impact biodiversity positively or negatively.

To engage financing and business leaders, the project hosts a series of stakeholder workshops. Business entities can be reached through other activities, such as social media and presentations. These activities were built on (and integrate the results of) the specific case studies from WP3.

Examples of businesses, with which the consortium targets to establish links, include PROTEUS Partnership, TNFD partners, Natural Capital organisations, World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD), Green Economy Coalition, EU Business@Biodiversity Platform.

The following table (Table 3) includes specific messages for businesses, listing their relevant outcomes, timeframe for realisation, channels and tools.

Table 3. Specific messages for businesses. Source: Authors' own work.

Category	Message
What do we offer them? Why should they be interested in the project/results? How could they benefit from the results of the project? What do we want them to do?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity loss is mainly triggered by the dominant global economic system – hence we need businesses to contribute to transformative changes. • Businesses contribute to biodiversity loss because of unsustainable practices, but with transformative changes and changing their values system, they can contribute to saving biodiversity and the society. • The current consumption practices have long-term destructive and detrimental effects on both nature and human health and well-being. • We need transformative change in the system to survive. • Making positive decisions for biodiversity businesses can answer the emerging “green” consumer needs better and reach a wider audience (consumers). • “More sustainable” businesses can make a significant impact. • They can manage and sustain their own resources better. • Transformative change can boost resilient production, higher quality of food, water and raw material security; understanding of new market demands; adaptation to climate change, early adaptation to future policies (fashion case study). • They can offer “greener” solutions to their respective market (finance case study). • They can diversify your portfolio.

Relevant outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D5.8 – Three comprehensive guidelines tailored for enabling players (civil society, policymakers and businesses). • WP3 outcomes, WP4 outcomes
Timeframe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From M6
Channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshops and consultations • Social media • Newsletter • Media-news
Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Briefs • Infographics • Illustrated transformative change stories

4.4 Civil society

Civil society organisations (e.g. NGOs) play a crucial role in shaping the social, political and economic landscape of any society. One of the key reasons for their importance is their ability to reach and influence a broad segment of the population. Civil societies have existing channels, credibility and resources to engage with people from different backgrounds. Moreover, civil societies have further resources to reach a wide segment of society.

The project provides guidance and support for target groups within the civil society sector to not only communicate better about biodiversity issues but also to be a catalysator for influencing policies to have greater societal impacts.

The project has aimed to reach three different groups that can be categorised under the term civil society:

- 1) Conservation NGOs working at EU and international levels (e.g. members of the European Habitats Forum including WWF, BirdLife, IUCN, Friends of the Earth, European Environmental Bureau, ClientEarth, OCEANA, FERN, Justice and Environment, Indigenous and Community Conserved Areas (ICCA), RARE, GreenPeace, etc.)
- 2) Social NGOs working on the local level with communities (consortium partners and their relevant networks – focusing on social issues such as gender, inclusion, diversity, migration, SDGs, etc.)
- 3) Organisations of sectoral groups – e.g. European Landowners' Organisation (ELO), Copa Cogeca, International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements (IFOAM), Forestry and Trade Associations.

The following table (Table 4) includes specific messages for target groups within the civil society, listing their relevant outcomes, timeframe for realisation, channels and tools.

Table 4. Specific messages for target groups within the civil society. Source: Authors' own work.

Category	Message
<p>What do we offer them?</p> <p>Why should they be interested in the project/results?</p> <p>How could they benefit from the results of the project?</p> <p>What do we want them to do?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using the project's outcomes (and the knowledge generated in the project about biodiversity, nature-based solutions and ecosystem services) the organisations can communicate and influence decisions better about biodiversity towards their own target audience. • The project outcomes can help them to trigger transformative change. • Their biodiversity relevant communication can be stronger, sharper and more impactful. • They can improve their cooperation and engagement with their stakeholders. • They can plan and organise more impactful campaigns and do advocacy more effectively. • The project offers guidance and training to help their work to reach greater impacts for biodiversity. • They can be empowered with new knowledge of how to communicate relevant information in the best way in order to nudge and drive policy and action to halt biodiversity loss.
Relevant outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D5.8 – Three comprehensive guidelines tailored for enabling players (civil society, policymakers and businesses). • Trainings • WP3 outcomes, WP4 outcomes
Timeframe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From M13
Channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trainings • Workshops • Social media • Newsletter • Media-news
Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training materials • Guidelines • Briefs • Infographics • Illustrated transformative change stories

4.5 Scientific community, researchers

The scientific community and researchers can benefit greatly from the results of the PLANET4B project. The results of the project can help advance scientific knowledge by uncovering new information about biodiversity loss and the factors that contribute to it. It can also help identify the gaps in our understanding of the topic. This can be conducive to guide future research efforts and ensure that we focus our efforts on the most important areas.

Future research projects have already been capitalised on PLANET4B (such as DAISY), providing policymakers with further information they need to make informed decisions ensuring that policies continue to be based on the most recent scientific results. The project likely inspired researchers from different disciplines and backgrounds to collaborate contributing to the formation of interdisciplinary teams and facilitate the exchange of ideas and expertise due to the over 60 scientific events and 20 joint actions with other research projects.

Specific target groups have been representatives of natural science, behavioural science, social science and gender studies focusing on intersectionality, authors of IPBES assessments and IPCC reports, science-policy interfaces (e.g. Eklipse, NetworkNature) researchers in sister projects and other Horizon Europe projects dealing with behavioural theories and transformative change, who have been reached by our continuously updated website, social media posts, joint events, scientific presentations, scientific articles and consultations.

The following table (Table 5) includes specific messages for scientific communities, listing their relevant outcomes, timeframe for realisation, channels and tools.

Table 5. Specific messages for scientific communities. Source: Authors' own work.

Category	Message
What do we offer them? Why should they be interested in the project/results? How could they benefit from the results of the project? What do we want them to do?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PLANET4B provides specific results and background from the activities to apply transdisciplinary research. Transdisciplinary research can provide applicable knowledge for decision making relevant to biodiversity. Transdisciplinary research has the potential to address unanswered questions in conventional scientific fields.
Relevant outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Outcomes of WP1 and WP2 Presentations on conferences, events Scientific articles
Timeframe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Throughout the project
Channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website Social media Newsletter

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conferences, networking events with similar projects • Scientific magazines
Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publications • Presentations • News

4.6 Youth, educators and social movements

To trigger transitions and transformations, the project increases capacities of youth and education organisations by providing online training resources and guidance. To aid its application among youth groups and movements, a set of educational resources (e.g. creative exercises; interactive games to raise awareness and reflection on biodiversity) are provided for the secondary and higher curricula as well as other extra-curricular educational settings and organisations (e.g. youth groups, movements, etc.).

Extension of materials and dissemination among schools (along with its adjustment to climate change materials) will be ensured through the consortium partner TEHRA (previously CAC) that directly works with schools throughout the EU. Academic partners and universities will also provide dissemination in higher education on a global scale. Exploitation of the learning materials will be completed after the project closing.

Specific target groups are school networks of the EU, universities and youth movements – e.g. Fridays for Future, Youth and Environment Europe (YEE), Young Friends of the Earth, Education for Climate Community, European SchoolNet. Youth and education organisations are addressed through the website and social media channels as well as dedicated dissemination.

The following table (Table 6) includes specific messages for the youth and educators, listing their relevant outcomes, timeframe for realisation, channels and tools.

Table 6. Specific messages for the youth and educators. Source: Authors' own work.

Category	Message
What do we offer them? Why should they be interested in the project/results? How could they benefit from the results of the project? What do we want them to do?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using the project's outcomes (and the knowledge generated in the project about biodiversity, nature-based solutions and ecosystem services) the organisations can communicate and influence decisions better about biodiversity towards their own target audience. • The project outcomes can help them to trigger transformative change. • Their biodiversity relevant communication can be stronger, sharper and more impactful. • They can improve their cooperation and engagement with their stakeholders. • They can plan and organise more impactful campaigns and do advocacy more effectively. • The project offers guidance and training to help their work to reach greater impacts for biodiversity.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They can be empowered with new knowledge of how to communicate relevant information in the best way in order to nudge and drive policy and action to halt biodiversity loss.
<p>What do we offer them?</p> <p>Why should they be interested in the project/results?</p> <p>How could they benefit from the results of the project?</p> <p>What do we want them to do?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using the project outcomes, they can communicate better about biodiversity issues. • They can influence policymakers to make more effective biodiversity policy implementations. • They can raise awareness, promote new attitudes and inspire actions of their target groups.
Relevant outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D5.9 – Online training and educational resources for communicating biodiversity and triggering transformative change. • D5.10 – Adjusted training materials for secondary and higher education.
Timeframe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • M30–M36
Channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trainings • Social media • Newsletter • Conferences • Meetings, bilateral consultations
Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online training resources

4.7 Local communities

Empowered communities can actively contribute to safeguarding biodiversity and implement nature-based solutions. These communities have been reached locally and through organisations and networks. They have also been reached through the case studies of the project with similar messages to the general public as well as locally relevant messages.

4.8 General public

Biodiversity loss affects every aspect of our lives including our health, economy and overall well-being – communicating about the project and its results can not only increase the visibility of the project and help to disseminate its results but also raise awareness of the topic of biodiversity.

Communicating about biodiversity loss (and the importance of our decisions) to a general public is needed to sensitise the issue. This can inspire individuals and communities to take action to protect and conserve biodiversity. By educating people about the importance of biodiversity, they can be encouraged to make lifestyle changes

that reduce their impact on the environment, support conservation efforts and advocate for policies that protect biodiversity.

In addition, communicating about biodiversity loss can help bridge the gap between scientists and the public. Scientific research on biodiversity loss can be complex and technical, making it difficult for non-experts to understand. By translating scientific findings into accessible language and presenting them in engaging ways, people can learn about the importance of biodiversity and the urgency of protecting it.

The general public can be informed through the project news (website and newsletter) and social media activities as well as other popular media posts, videos and podcasts.

Since one of the project's main questions has been how biodiversity is currently perceived, the project's findings can be used to enhance its own communication activities (EO 1 – information on relevant messages of biodiversity communication⁴).

The following table (Table 7) includes messages for the general public which can be fine-tuned based on the project's findings. Questions to be asked in this fine-tuning process are: Why should the general public care about the project? Why is it interesting/valuable for people? What aspect of the project can be interesting for them? (see also CBD, Global Biodiversity Outlook 5⁵ and WWF, Understanding Biodiversity Awareness in 9 countries⁶).

Table 7. Messages and examples for general public. Source: Authors' own work.

Category	Message
(The importance of) biodiversity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> We rely on biodiversity for our very existence. It provides us with the basic ecosystem services that allow us to survive and thrive.
Biodiversity loss, scale of the problem, consequences, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alarming and continued loss of biodiversity now threatens both the biosphere and human life because of inapt governance. Over-consumption is an important driver in biodiversity loss.
The importance of decisions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> We make decisions almost every day that can affect biodiversity. We can also influence biodiversity related decisions.
The project – how it works, what solutions we plan to provide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> See section 3.1 General messages of the project.

⁴ REA (2022). Grant Agreement: Project 101082212 – PLANET4B. Part B, p.5.

⁵ CBD (2020). Global Biodiversity Outlook 5. Available from <https://www.cbd.int/gbo5>. Access: April 24th, 2023.

⁶ WWF (2022). Understanding Biodiversity Awareness in 9 countries. Available from https://wwfint.awsassets.panda.org/downloads/wwf_global_biodiversity_awareness_study_2022_only_numbers.pdf. Access: April 24th, 2023.

5. Communication and Dissemination Plan

5.1 Phases of communication

All PPs have been actively involved in communication and dissemination activities to achieve the expected impact of the project. By utilising the potentials of the planned channels (e.g. website, social media, newsletter, media contacts, participation in different events) and networks of the PPs, the project has the potential to multiply the effects of disseminating the project results which requires the active participation of the PPs. The distribution of communication and dissemination tasks is based on the project outputs and milestones and the agreement by the PPs (Table 8). Ensuring the highest level of credibility and competence, the communication tasks are aligned with the strengths and capacities of the partner in charge.

Table 8. Overview of main communication and dissemination activities. Source: Authors' own work.

Phase	Main focus, activities, objective
Initial phase, M1–M6	<p>The first phase is about kick-starting the communication and dissemination activities. The main goal is to create a solid base for the upcoming activities (visual identity, designing the website, setting up internal communication).</p> <p>By the end of this phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visual identity (logo, branding, templates, etc.) is ready and shared with the PPs. • Website is fully operational (contents are uploaded, there is at least one news article). • Social media activities have started (few “warm-up” contents). <p>Some project meetings and presentations are organised.</p>
Operational phase, from M6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broader communication activities start once the website is fully operational and at least one main/key deliverable is available on it. • Social media activities are intensified, news on the project website are published (and further disseminated via the newsletter) and meetings and workshops with key actors are held during this period. In addition, we inform the global/regional media about the project via press releases.
Maturity phase, close to the end of the project (M30–M36)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Here, the main focus is on the promotion of the concrete results, the final findings/outputs.
Additional phase, after the end of the project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Making sure that the outcomes are available after the project ends (activities for five years after the end of the project). • PPs will follow the dissemination and exploitation activities after the project closing to ensure the effective use of project results. For the detailed dissemination and exploitation plan, see Chapter 10. Exploitation and Dissemination.

5.2 Project Partner's responsibilities and workflow

The Communication and Dissemination WP leader (GD), the contributing PPs and the project coordination team (PCT including MLU and CU) work together for effective communication dissemination and exploitation of project results and outcomes.

Tasks and responsibilities of WP5 leader Good Issue (GD):

- Being responsible for the coordination and monitoring processes of Task 5.1 and Task 5.2.
- Creating and regularly revising the Communication Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) strategy that is in line with the EU guidance⁷, compiling the updated deliverable in M18 and M35.
- Coordinating the communication and dissemination activities among the PPs.
- Based on the CDE strategy, creating an annual work plan of communication and dissemination tasks, closely linked to the defined outcomes, goals and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).
- Co-planning and monitoring PPs' communication and dissemination activities.
- Supporting and supervising of PPs' CDE related tasks.
- Managing the website and social media channels to ensure structured visibility of the outcomes.
- Providing templates and guidelines for the public communication and dissemination as well as visual identity and branding elements.
- Supporting the project outcomes through the promotion of materials and communication tools.
- Contributing to the reporting system using WP5 related outcomes.
- Organisation of regular meetings of the Communication Committee (COMCOM) with PPs to discuss all tasks, responsibilities and challenges related to communication and dissemination. The main means of internal communication between COMCOM members is email.

Responsibilities and tasks of the project coordination team (MLU-CU) related to CDE activities:

- Keeping the WP5 leader (GD) informed about the progress of the project and the main outcomes of the discussions related to communication and dissemination activities with the Advisory Board and the European Research Executive Agency (REA) to ensure the proper update of the CDE strategy and plan daily activities. The main communication tool used for communications are emails and bilateral meetings every three months.
- Approving and reviewing the project communication deliverables and outputs.
- Participating in COMCOM meetings and updating internal project management work plan (Miro board) according to the information provided by the PPs.

⁷ European Commission (2020). H2020 Online Manual. Communicating Your Project. Available from https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm. Access: April 25th, 2023.

Responsibilities and tasks of all PPs related to CDE activities

Implementing effective, competent and reliable communication and dissemination activities – all PPs are involved in the CDE activities and contribute to reach the project level of KPIs undertaken in the Grant Agreement:

- Delegating one person per organisation to the COMCOM. The delegate takes part in the COMCOM meetings and follows the work of the COMCOM.
- Giving inputs to the communication management team (deliverables, reports, articles, photos, events, etc.) on their related activities.
- Adhering to the compulsory visibility elements according to the Grant Agreement Article 17 and the visual identity guideline provided by GD.
- Providing communication and dissemination content according to the annual CDE plan.
- Utilising their existing communication channels on local, national and transnational level (website, social media, newsletter, conferences, events, media lists, etc.) and networks (stakeholders, target groups) to promote PLANET4B's outcomes by sharing the results of the project.
- Reporting on their CDE activities regularly (every six months) following the reporting templates developed by the PCT and GD together.

6. Communication channels and tools

6.1 Visual identity

The visual identity and its practical application (templates) have played a critical role in communicating/disseminating the project and its results in a coherent and outstanding way. The visual identity builds on the logo and its elements (shape and colour). The appearance of the logo is simple, but strong, easy to recognise and easy to use. It refers to the name "planet" (concentric circles), biodiversity as our main topic (colours), and also evokes "action" (influence, decision, triggering change, etc. – "target" structure).

In the project's visual communication, we use the following elements: fonts, colour palette, logo, logo variations, logo elements (circular pattern), presentation, deliverable and social media post templates, photos as well as rollup.

Since it is difficult to illustrate the project's complex and abstract concepts (such as "decision-making", "biodiversity related decisions", "transformative change", "biodiversity related values, behaviours and norms", etc.) in the visual communication (website, social media posts, etc.) we have used simple, general but strong pictures to accompany the project communication. These pictures are either showing:

- a) positive biodiversity examples (natural forests, green scenery, animals, conservation pictures, etc.) or
- b) images about biodiversity loss.

We have avoided using staged⁸ and symbolic pictures (e.g. globe, etc. in a human hand). When using pictures with people⁹ we intend to choose an illustration that is as authentic as possible.

The visual identity was explained in the Brand Guideline, shared with the consortium. PPs use the visual elements through their social media posts, presentation and report (deliverable) templates, etc.

Visibility and Use of Funders' Logos

PLANET4B receives EU and non-EU funds – UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) and State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) from Switzerland – for the project implementation. Pursuant to the legal agreements with the funder organisations, in any public communication and dissemination activities of the PPs, the logos and acknowledgement of funding must be indicated (see project Brand Guideline). The relevant rules are laid down in the Grant Agreement (Art. 17) and in separate agreements with UKRI and SERI.

6.2 Written contents

Addressing the communication challenge we face (e.g. an overcrowded communication sphere), we have applied a set of rules to our written communication that are consistent with the EU communication guidelines and the latest trends in science communication. When communicating about the results of the project, it has been important to use a language, a style, and an approach that is clear, concise and accessible to a wide range of audiences.

Wherever possible, in our communication we have used clear and simple language and messages that avoid using jargon or technical terms that may be unfamiliar to non-experts. Where necessary, we defined any technical terms. We tried to avoid overly technical or complex explanations and instead focus on the description of our findings in a way that is easy to understand. By doing so, we can help ensure the research results are understood and valued by a diverse audience, contributing to the goal of creating a greater societal impact.

6.3 Website

The PLANET4B website (<https://planet4b.eu/>) is the main interface for communication with the public and has been updated regularly. The website traffic is monitored using Google Analytics which provides data on users and their interactions with the website.

Beyond the main function of introducing the project and the participants the website:

- makes the results (deliverables) easily available for download and use through a clear and accessible structure;

⁸ A staged photograph, also known as a stock photograph, is an image that is taken with the purpose of being licensed and used in various media, such as advertisements, websites, and magazines. Photos of this kind are usually shot in a controlled environment, with models or objects carefully arranged and posed to convey a particular message or idea.

⁹ The use of photographs picturing people will always follow the principles of the Data Management Plan (DMP) of PLANET4B: it requires ethical considerations, including obtaining consent, respecting privacy, avoiding misrepresentation, respecting ownership and avoiding exploitation.

- shares news, articles, events;
- attracts audience for the newsletter;
- builds up trust by transparency (sharing information about the project, the participants, etc.).

The website is operated by GD under the supervision of the PCT.

The website structure is as follows:

Main/opening (home) page

The opening page is technically a quick snapshot of the project using short information bits in a scroll-down structure. Its elements are: banner slide (3–4 moving banners; one shows a project slogan another promotes a report or an event), project description (short description with a “read more” option), latest news (2–3 of the latest or most important news), partners (logos of the PPs), “sign up for newsletter” panel, “ask the expert” panel, contact, social media icons (LinkedIn, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube), disclaimer/privacy policy, etc.

About

The project: a short description of the goal(s) of the project and its main activities. Partners: introduction of the PPs with a short description of the respective organisation and its role in the project. Team members: name, photo, link to LinkedIn profile.

Case studies

Collection of 11 stories (case studies). Each case study on this page has a sub-page with the accompanying information (plus photos, videos, etc.) that has been updated as the case study progressed.

Library

Project documents: all the deliverables and outputs (reports, articles, etc.) are uploaded for download. The website uses tags for choosing between the type (report/article/brief/policy, paper/training material, etc.) as well as the topic/category of the document (communication/decision, making/transformational change, etc.) Media: newsletters, press releases, logo book.

News

News: news about the projects, its outcomes, similar projects, etc. and other related contents (interviews, blog entries, etc.). Events: participation in public events (conferences, workshops, etc.) related to the PLANET4B project; contributions of PPs (e.g. presentation, panel discussion, poster, etc.) are promoted on the website.

Further updates on the website were realised to ensure featuring transformational change guides and metadata sheets.

Number of website visitors planned: 5.000 (achieved).

Operation of the Website after project closing

The website will be available for 5 years after the project closing. The domain and website host is booked until 2030 by GD.

The aim of the website after the project closing is to serve as a repository of knowledge that can be referenced for dissemination. Since the project is closed, there will be no further modifications and publications on the website.

In case of a technical problem, GD will act with the involvement of an IT expert.

6.4 Social media channels

PLANET4B has aimed to have a strong presence in social media, enhancing the outreach to its target audience and the broader public. To ensure the maximum of usability and exploitation and to make the best use of the already developed social media networks of the PPs the focus has been given to those social media that PPs have been using regularly and successfully to communicate and interact with their partners and other stakeholders.

Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram and YouTube (see Table 9) have been selected as the most appropriate social networks to promote the project achievements, news and outcomes. Regarding the communication about the project and the dissemination of its results we have primarily used the project's own social media channels. While LinkedIn and Twitter were used to reach specific target groups, Instagram served as a tool to address the general public. The project's YouTube channel functions as a platform to have access to the project's video contents (e.g. videoclips from workshops).

To ensure that all relevant target groups are regularly addressed, the responsibility also lied with the PPs to make frequent use of their institutes' channels – website, newsletter and social media (see Table 10). In addition, we built on the potentials of other projects under the Horizon Europe calls. Together with the PPs, GD reached out to communication teams of other projects or organisations as part of Task 5.3 of WP5 in order to involve them in the planned communication activities.

Fitting into their own social media routine, PPs (as well as individuals) were also encouraged to develop their own contents – not just to repost PLANET4B news and contents but to post information on events they attended, workshops they organised or any other content relating to PLANET4B topics. Since these posts are designed to address individuals to be using a more personal tone, they mobilised a different level of potential in the communication and dissemination activities.

PLANET4B social media links:

- <https://www.linkedin.com/in/planet4b-project/>
- <https://twitter.com/Planet4bProject>
- <https://www.instagram.com/planet4b/>
- <https://www.youtube.com/@horizoneuropeplanet4b>

Official hashtag: #PLANET4B

Other recommended hashtags: #biodiversity, #transformativechange #policy
#governance #pluralvalues #intersectionality #time4betterdecisions
#behaviourchange

Number of social media followers planned: 1.000 (exceeded).

Number of social media posts planned: 700 (exceeded).

Based on the feedback of our project partners, we have identified several areas for improvement in our social media engagement strategies. These suggestions aimed at enhancing interaction, increasing reach, and fostering a more active and participatory community among our stakeholders.

Key Suggestions for Enhancing Social Media Engagement

Increasing Partner Participation:

- By heightened tagging of partner and other organisations involved in our project in social media posts, we could raise even more awareness amongst the partners and foster engagement.
- Creative recognition strategies, such as highlighting actively engaged partners or creating internal awards for contributions, could be implemented to encourage further participation.
- Promoting personal stories and career insights of project members could help us create a more personal connection with our audience.

Content Creation and Diversity:

- Further encouraging partners to create and share their own content related to the project could enrich our social media presence with diverse perspectives and experiences.
- Providing partners with social media templates and even more support in content development might assist those who are less experienced with social media.
- Employing further a variety of content types, such as infographics and videos, could enhance engagement with different audience segments.
- Extending our social media post calendar for regular contributions from partners might streamline our content distribution.

Effective Use of Platforms:

- Tailoring even more content specifically for each social media platform, like polls, might increase interaction and relevance.
- Leveraging LinkedIn's strength in engaging specific target groups, and Instagram's appeal to the general public could optimise our platform usage.
- Increasing Twitter engagement through even more frequent and relevant posts could improve our presence on this platform.

Cross-Promotion and Collaboration:

- Initiating more extensive cross-promotion by sharing and reposting content from partner organisations and sister projects could amplify our reach and impact.
- More widely collaborating with the communication teams of partner institutions might lead to a more coordinated and effective promotion strategy.
- Seeking further opportunities for joint communication initiatives with other projects and organisations might expand our network and influence.

Responsive and Interactive Engagement:

- Creating an environment that encourages replies, comments, and discussions could make our social media channels more interactive and engaging.
- Implementing interactive elements like Q&A sessions might actively involve our audience and foster a sense of community.

Targeting and Reaching Broader Audiences:

- Further fine-tuning and understanding the target groups for each social media platform could help us tailor our content more effectively.
- Utilising insights from analytics to refine our content strategies might enable us to reach broader audiences, including key stakeholders and the general public.

Table 9. PLANET4B relevant platforms and contents. Source: Authors' own work.

Platform	Content
Social media of PLANET4B (Twitter/X, LinkedIn, Instagram, YouTube)	Sharing different contents (see the post types below)
Social media of PPs (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram, YouTube)	Sharing the main project news/results by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • reposting the PLANET4B's social media contents • developing their own contents (attending events, etc.)
Social media of PPs' individuals (Twitter/X, LinkedIn, Instagram)	Sharing the main project news/results, short news about meetings, events, etc. but also personal insights by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • reposting the PLANET4B's social media contents • creating their own contents

Table 10. Existing social media channels of the PPs Source: Authors' own work.

PP	LinkedIn	Twitter/X	Instagram	YouTube	Facebook
MLU	26k	12.2k	17.1k	3.36k	31k
MLU/SLEG Lab	5	–	–	–	–
NINA	7k	1258	2380	7.36k	13k
CU/CAWR	2 k	2.5k	–	–	2.5K
UNEP-WCMC	58k	21.6k	–	–	70k
CGE	0,2 k	170	1.3k	20	3.8k
CAC/TEHRA	–	–	400	–	–
DC	–	–	800	–	2.4k
FUG	–	–	–	–	600
CG	17	750	300	84	2.2k

ESSRG	1k	200	–	175	–
IFZ	67	600	500	–	–
GD	–	–	–	–	250
OOF	6	48.7k	308k	5.2k	237k
RU	167k	30.8k	27.7k	6.9k	44k
FIBL	14k	5.9k	–	–	7k
UNIPI	135k	19.5k	34.3k	6k	70k

Post types:

- News about deliverables (short summary, keywords, background, importance, link, etc.)
- Promoting short interviews of key persons/partner organisations
- Introducing partner organisations (their role, etc.)
- Upcoming events, conferences
- Upcoming workshops (promotion of workshops)
- Promoting sister project(s)
- News outside of the project
- Promoting the newsletter
- Promoting the “Ask the Expert” option
- Posts on Instagram about successful diversity campaigns and visuals (UN, WWF, Greenpeace, etc.)

The visuals accompanying the posts are produced by GD using project branded Canva templates. If necessary, the editable visuals are also shared with the PPs to make their own posts.

Quick social media guideline

Below we provide some guidance for PPs about how to use social media:

- Use a language/tone that fits your audience. You could ask them a question or use a quote or a set of emojis and encourage them to comment under your post and share their experience.
- Use appropriate language and tone when posting on social media. Avoid using overly technical language or jargon.
- Make it clear that you are affiliated with a particular institution or organisation. This can help to establish your credibility and avoid confusion about your role and authority.
- Avoid discussing controversial topics that are unrelated to your research. This can help to avoid potential conflicts and ensure that your social media presence remains professional.
- Use multimedia content: visual communication is a very important aspect of all social media channels. Images, videos, infographics, factoids, quotes, etc. catch the user’s attention much faster and effectively than text on its own. This kind of content can easily be used to tell a story and helps to engage the audience emotionally. You can use the PLANET4B social media templates in Canva.

- When posting graphs use a clear title that briefly explains the findings. Keep graphs simple (under about 10 data points). This may mean highlighting just a portion of a graph or data from the report.
- When writing a post on social media try to keep the number of words around 10–20 (posting with photo) and 30–40 words (posting without photo). Word count includes all words (dates, names, sources, etc. – everything).

Consider the platform you are posting on and the norms and expectations of that platform carefully. For example, Twitter has a character limit, while LinkedIn is more focused on professional networking.

For more tips: “Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects”.¹⁰

After the project life cycle social media activities should reflect on project closed status. Channels and profiles will not be updated. Admin/Editor rights can be shared upon request with MLU/CU.

6.5 Newsletter

Six PLANET4B bi-annual e-Newsletters have been released, offering the project community an overview of the latest project activities and developments. E-Newsletters are both uploaded on the project website and distributed to a list of recipients. The newsletter aims to enable the subscribers to get first-hand information about the project and other projects related to PLANET4B as well as relevant and important news about our main topics.

The newsletter is created through MailChimp, a web-based email marketing service. It is distributed to a mailing list containing subscriber information gathered through a sign-up form on the website. PPs may also promote the newsletter through their channels. An unsubscribe/opt-out link is available as per EU directive 2002/58/EC.

GD coordinates the editing of the newsletter. A mailing template was designed for this purpose. The sender is a dedicated email: info@planet4b.eu.

For the promotion of the newsletter, the following channels are used:

- Social media posts
- Website
- Channels of the PPs’ institutes (website, social media channels, newsletters, events, etc.)
- Direct email (when contacting a target group, a line should be added to the email about subscribing to the newsletter)

¹⁰ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research & Innovation (2020). H2020 Programme. Guidance Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects. Available from: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-med-guide_en.pdf. Access: April 25th, 2023.

6.6 Briefs

Short summaries (creative briefs) are created of each deliverable enabling results relevant to enabling players. These short briefs are based on the deliverable, using its relevant sections (executive summary, key findings, etc.) and any additional information provided by the author(s) of the deliverable. All briefs are also uploaded on the website.

The briefs are prepared in cooperation of the Task leads and edited by GD.

6.7 Press releases

To further promote the project and its results, press releases have been created in case of major project news such as policy recommendations or substantial project results to be communicated to a wider audience. Press releases have been prepared and shared with major European news organisations such as EurActiv, Politico, Policy Review, Reuters and other pan-European news agencies (other examples: ESG Today, Sustain Europe).

Depending on the relevance, PPs will also translate and share information with their own national, regional or local media contacts (both specialised and professional contacts). All press releases will be uploaded on the website as well. PPs will translate and set the press release (provided by GD) to their cultural context and will disseminate it through their media contacts.

6.8 Scientific and non-scientific publications

Scientific publications represent an important means of project result dissemination. The published scientific papers have been targeting academics, researchers and relevant professionals. Non-scientific publications have the potential to reach a wider, general and professional audience.

Scientific publications have been published (and sent/uploaded to the scientific sites/magazines) by the PPs, non-scientific publications are published by the PPs, and shared by GD.

Interviews (opinions) of experts within the partner organisations were also created, attracting media attention on the specific topics.

Guidelines (know-how) on:

- Scientific articles:
<https://www.european-science.org/how-to-write-a-scientific-article/>
- Popular science articles:
<https://royalsociety.org/blog/2017/08/writing-popular-science-as-a-scientist/>

Number of scientific articles planned: 5 (exceeded).

Number of non-scientific articles planned: 30 (exceeded).

6.9 Emails

One of the primary means of stakeholder outreach in PLANET4B was one-on-one email to inform interested parties about project results, events and activities. We also use emails to distribute our newsletter to stakeholders drawing attention to the project's highlights. Emails allowed PPs to conduct a small-scale targeted outreach with a more personal rhetoric; however, while email is a simple form of communication, it can be difficult to strategically plan and measure its effectiveness.

6.10 Open-source platforms

The project's key deliverables and relevant open access data will also be shared on open-source platforms such as OER Commons, OpenSDG, Zenodo and OpenAIRE.

6.11 Events

PPs have disseminated deliverables by participating in national and international scientific conferences as well as international EU policy and business events in order to further promote the project and engage other stakeholders while raising awareness of the PLANET4B activities and expected results. The PPs represented the consortium and attended debates, lead debates, deliver project-related speeches, contact stakeholders and/or carry out workshops.

PPs have informed the PCT as well as the communication team about their contribution before attending events. After the event, PPs shared the material communicated (e.g. presentation) with any other relevant information so the communication team could create content (news, posts, etc.) about it.

To enable the tracking of relevant events including scientific conferences and policy events, (channelling outcomes to accelerate change) a database was created and featured on the internal communication platform on SharePoint as part of Task 5.4 of WP5.

6.12 Consultations

Key enabling players (mostly EU and UN decision-makers, business representatives, civil society members, relevant EU and global projects and initiatives) have been contacted and informed about the project and its results through bilateral in-person or electronic consultations. Additionally, through WP3 and its series of learning communities, local level stakeholders have been regularly consulted.

Stories of transformative change from the case studies' relevant places and sectors and economic value chains are compiled. Transformation pathways are produced. These outputs of PLANET4B as well as relevant interventions have been discussed with key enabling players among the target audience in order to enable upscaling at EU and global levels through these consultations.

Number of planned consultations: 10 (exceeded).

6.13 Other visual tools

Accompanying the promotion of the different outputs, simple but creative infographics are created by the PPs using their own resources to aid their reports or social media activities. Supporting the final results of the project, Case Study videos have been developed under the supervision of GD.

6.14 Media relations

Apart from the press releases, PPs shared information about the results of the projects through their own existing media relations in order to generate TV and radio presence in the local/regional media.

7. Synergies and accelerating changes

7.1 The Synergies Strategy

To maximise the project's impact, synergies with other relevant Horizon Europe and non-Horizon projects and initiatives were mapped, connection and cooperation are established, and joint work and outputs (e.g. press releases, posts, events) have been initiated under Task 5.3 (Mapping synergies and creating cooperation with existing initiatives and projects) of WP5. The main dissemination tools of the project have been continuously worked on and reflected in line with the target groups and the mapping and synergies seeking activities.

The Synergies Strategy (D5.5) outlines how collaboration with external projects and initiatives whose areas of work have synergies with PLANET4B. In this strategy, different types of collaborations are defined, types of projects and initiatives to collaborate with are outlined as well as a timeline for collaboration. This includes a seven-step process (identifying, assessing, contacting, coordinating and implementing, communicating, monitoring, setting future collaboration) detailing how to work with external partners based on the identified synergies. Therefore, the primary focus of the Synergies Strategy is to act as an internal guidance document for PPs. A database of over 70 EU and international projects and initiatives has been created listing all cooperation activities with external projects and initiatives (D5.6).

7.2 Channelling outcomes to accelerate change

The aim of Task 5.4 was to communicate and disseminate the work and deliverables of PLANET4B through participation at national and international events, conferences and forums where there are opportunities to engage with audiences from the public sector, research communities, civil society and private sector. In order to ensure that these activities happen in a coordinated and impactful manner, UNEP-WCMC developed a template for partners to fill out at the planning stages in the lead up to the event (capturing succinct information on what the event is about and who the main audience is). Using this information, UNEP-WCMC coordinated with the relevant partner to identify and prioritise the most relevant information, messages and deliverables to disseminate at the event, based on the subject focus and audiences for the event. After the event has taken place, partners were asked to provide a brief summary of the outcomes of the event (e.g. what information and deliverables were

disseminated and to whom, how our participation contributed to PLANET4B's work and deliverables feeding into other areas of work and research etc). Collecting information from partners about how they have disseminated PLANET4B's work at external events in a timely manner was critical for making sure this information is being systematically collected (D5.7), ensuring impact monitoring.

8. Capacity building for enabling players

Task 5.5 Enhancing the capacity of enabling players and change agents to initiate transformative change was led by CU. Building on outcomes of WP1 and WP4 three practical guidelines for three target groups (civil society, policymakers and businesses) have been developed to provide detail on potential transformative pathways, intersectionality context, behaviour and creative methods and communication tips on biodiversity (D5.8).

An online training programme and educational resources (D5.9, D5.10) have been developed to involve all these materials for the target groups to aid biodiversity prioritisation. With specific extensions, the educational resources are also tailored for both secondary and higher education curricula.

The capacity-building materials tailored to different target groups are among the project's Key Exploitable Results, as they have the potential to generate wide-ranging transformative change through channels such as education, community learning, and community building. Therefore, Chapter 10. Exploitation deals in detail with how these outputs are delivered to the target groups and how their effective use is supported.

9. Internal communication

The purpose of the internal communication section is to ensure that the external communication tasks are carried out as efficiently as possible by all the consortium members. Furthermore, it aims to make communication and dissemination workflow (tasks, responsibilities, monitoring) transparent.

Planning and Management Tools

The basic tools that will be used during the project to accomplish the planning and carrying out of communication and dissemination activities among the PPs are:

- Communication and Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) strategy and plan: This document contains the main goals, tools and responsibilities on CDE activities of the consortium with key messages, main actors, channels and specific activities, timeline and KPIs. The document is renewed every six months.
- The project management work plan (Miro board): Miro board that contains all the PLANET4B activities, CDE activities and outcomes (deliverables, KPIs, milestones) as a detailed work plan of the consortium.
- COMCOM meeting: The Communication Committee (COMCOM) members meet online bi-monthly to share and discuss CDE related issues, refresh the project management work plan regarding CDE related tasks as well as prepare the renewing of the CDE plan.

Internal Communication Tools

The main tools of internal communication:

- Regular emails
- COMCOM, periodic meetings (online bi-monthly)
- WP leads meetings (online every four months)
- Steering Committee meetings (annually)

Intranet – SharePoint/Teams

PLANET4B project's main internal documentation and information sharing platform SharePoint/Teams has been provided by CU. This private tool will enhance the information exchange among all PPs (minutes, internal documents, WP's specific information, etc.) as well as facilitate internal coordination. The related communication and dissemination documents and plans can be found under the WP5 folder.

10. Exploitation and dissemination

10.1. Introduction & summary

The European Commission describes exploitation as “the utilisation of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.”¹¹

In the context of **Horizon Europe programme**, **exploitation** refers to using a project's results – whether tangible (like data, prototypes, software) or intangible (like knowledge, information, processes) – in further activities that go beyond the project's original goals. The ultimate aim is to ensure that research and innovation lead to real societal, economic, or environmental impact.

In case of PLANET4B, the exploitation strategy concentrates to boost the following activities with the results:

- Furthering research activities especially on behaviour and transdisciplinary science to gain knowledge on transformative change on decisions related to biodiversity.
- Developing, creating, and promoting education products triggering transformative change.
- Creating and providing education services triggering transformative change.
- Promoting policy or societal changes by providing comprehensive guidelines and catalogue of transformative intervention methods.

In PLANET4B the exploitation (or use) will be done through research activities, skills and educational training. It has been agreed that each partner takes measures to ensure ‘exploitation’ of its results by using the above and additional PLANET4B

¹¹European Commission (2023). EU Grants. AGA – Annotated Grant Agreement. EU Funding Programmes 2021-2027. Available from: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf. Access: April 25th, 2023.

outcomes and results in further research activities (outside the action). This activity will be pursued four years or beyond after the project's end.

Exploitation of their results will be performed either by individual partners directly especially the Key Exploitable Results but also other outcomes (e.g. for further research or for commercial exploitation in its own activities) or by others (other beneficiaries or third parties, e.g. through licensing or by transferring the ownership of results).

The consortium has agreed on an exploitation management system relying on the following pillars:

1. Intellectual Property (IP) Management & Access Rights

Ownership of the results will follow the ownership specifications in compliance with the clauses of the consortium agreement. Partners are also invited to check for “hidden traps” (publications, posters, etc), which might affect potential patentability, protect IP rights (e.g., patents, copyrights, trademarks) and define access rights for project partners to background knowledge and results.

2. Proactive monitoring of project outputs and KER exploitation

KER leaders are proactively managing the exploitation of their KER according to KER strategy. Management and protection of the project outputs carried out by WP leads and co-leads, supported by the project coordination team. Also, proactive monitoring of research outputs such as regular reviews must be made.

3. Dissemination of the project outputs for further exploitation

Coordination and WP leads and co-leads, scientists to be involved, in collaboration with the project lead MLU. Scientists ensure that electronic copies of peer-reviewed scientific publications become available in Zenodo <http://www.zenodo.org> (unless otherwise published in open access format). Other publications and dissemination materials along with deliverables will also be available on Zenodo to ensure a long-term life and accessibility.

10.2. Identification of Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

PLANET4B project has numerous deliverables, out of which we identified and elaborated five Key Exploitable Results with the help of the Horizon Booster Services. The **Horizon Results Booster** is a free service offered by the European Commission to beneficiaries of EU-funded research and innovation projects. It aims to maximise the impact of these projects by helping them effectively **disseminate** their results and, more importantly, **exploit** them to generate societal, economic, or environmental benefits.

The following KERs were identified:

- **D2.4 Catalogue of transformative intervention methods** for various enabling players.
- **D4.4 Knowledge products**, including synthesis of applicability of behaviour science and intersectionality for prioritising biodiversity into relevant EU and global processes.

- **D5.8 Three comprehensive guidelines** tailored for enabling players (civil society, policymakers, businesses).
- **D5.9 Online training and educational resources** for communicating biodiversity and triggering transformative change (elaboration is in progress with Go to market module).
- **D5.10 Adjusted training materials** for secondary and higher education.

Relevant partners responsible for the KERs attended the Horizon Results Booster¹² training that offered **tailored, expert support and coaching services** to project teams. These services are designed to help projects:

Identify and Characterise Key Exploitable Results (KERs): Experts work with project teams to pinpoint which of their research outcomes have the highest potential for impact and how to clearly describe their value proposition.

Work on the KERs Exploitation Strategies: This involves guiding the KERs through the process of outlining how their KERs will be used beyond the project's lifetime, including:

- **Commercial exploitation:** Developing business plans, market analyses, and strategies.
- **Non-commercial exploitation:** For results that aim for societal or policy impact, this includes strategies for standardisation, policy recommendations, or further research.
- **Manage Intellectual Property (IP):** Providing guidance on how to protect project results through patents, copyrights, trademarks, or other IP mechanisms, and defining clear access rights among project partners.
- **Enhance Dissemination Activities:** While exploitation focuses on using results, effective dissemination is key to reaching potential users. The Booster helps projects design promotional plans, identify target audiences, and select appropriate communication channels. This can include support for creating fact sheets, videos, webinars, or social media campaigns.
- **Go-to-Market Support:** For projects with commercial potential, the Booster offers specific help in preparing for market entry.

Given that our prior engagement with Boosting services focused on two Key Exploitable Results (KERs), this CDE (Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation) plan will detail the strategy for these two KERs in the subsequent chapter, while providing a less detailed overview for three additional KERs.

¹² Source: Horizon Booster Service: <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/ServicePacks/Details/55>

10.3. Insight into the exploitation plan of each Key Exploitable Results (KER) in the PLANET4B project

Table 11. Exploitation Intention Table of Key Exploitable Result 1 (KER1): Online training and educational resources for communicating biodiversity and triggering transformative change (D5.9).

<p>Description</p>	<p>An open-access online training and set of educational resources designed for facilitators working to engage people in conversations about biodiversity. The resource supports participant recruitment and inclusive communication, steering transformative change through tested creative methods and interventions. The site will also host practical tips, inspiring stories, and additional materials to help bring biodiversity into everyday conversations and actions. Many of the methods can be conducted within a short timeframe, increasing the range of people who could be reached.</p>
<p>Target market/ end users</p>	<p>Target market:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policymaking at local level as well as beyond • NGOs • Educational institutions who would be multipliers • Media • Businesses: Sector agnostic approach to companies, but focus on sustainability champions within enterprises <p>End users:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policymakers – mainly across local scales, but also national and international • Sustainability ambassadors within private sector businesses – or workers with a vested interest in sustainability • Researchers • Climate influencers (e.g. climate ambassadors) • NGOs and Civil Society groups: biodiversity charities (mostly as partners/channels)
<p>Competitive advantages</p>	<p>Compared to existing similar solutions, the PLANET4B training offers method-specific and group-specific materials, with insights on how to adapt methods to biodiversity. Further comparative advantage is that it incorporates the experiences of five PLANET4B case studies from UK, Norway, Austria, Germany, and Switzerland, where both biodiversity and inclusivity are key considerations in implementation.</p> <p>The training responds to a strong demand for quick, adaptable methods that can be used in settings such as doorstep conversations or pop-up events, where practitioners may only have a few minutes to engage. It includes practical materials such as guiding questions, downloadable information sheets, and step-by-step methods tailored for ease of use.</p>

Use model	<p>Service: The Key Exploitable Result (KER) will be implemented as an online training service. The resources will be delivered within training programmes tailored to specific target groups, including businesses, policymakers, higher education institutions, and civil society, NGO organisations. These modules can be adapted for use in internal training, blended learning formats, or public awareness-raising campaigns.</p> <p>Early Adopters:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project partners and their extended networks • Learning communities that actively participated in the PLANET4B project • Local policymakers and NGOs who contributed to the initial market research and expressed a need for accessible, engaging tools
Partners	<p>Leader of the exploitation process: Coventry University</p> <p>Contributor partners: Climate Academy, Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg, ESSRG, IFZ, University of Pisa, CzechGlobe, Radboud University</p>
Timing	2025
IP status	<p>Creative Commons license (e.g. CC0 or CC-BY) will be applied. The license will be carefully selected, taking into consideration Intellectual Property Rights.</p>

Table 12. Exploitation Roadmap of Key Exploitable Result 1 (KER1): Online training and educational resources for communicating biodiversity and triggering transformative change (D5.9).

Actions	<p>In the 3 to 6 months following the project's end, the focus will be on consolidating and embedding the training within relevant networks. While the four course modules will be fully available at the end of the project (targeting policymakers, businesses, researchers, and civil society), this period will involve ensuring smooth functionality across the custom-built platform, addressing any minor technical or content updates (such as broken links), and finalising user guidance. Although the training is not intended to be monetised, the platform will remain active and open access for at least three years, hosting this and potentially other related training resources. Basic maintenance will be ensured by project partners, with updates undertaken as needed. All content is GDPR compliant, and permissions have been secured for all voices included. This phase may also involve light-touch dissemination activities, such as showcasing the course at conferences, presenting to relevant networks, and collecting user feedback. These actions will support the ongoing visibility and usability of the course and may inform future training initiatives or proposals.</p>
----------------	---

Roles	The Centre for Agroecology, Water and Resilience (CAWR) at Coventry University will be the main organisation responsible for the training exploitation roadmap and its continued visibility and accessibility post-project. CAWR will oversee the hosting and maintenance of the course website for at least three years, ensuring it remains accessible and technically functional, with minor updates where needed.
Milestones	<p>Milestone: Website fully functional with four course tracks (Policy, Business, Research, Civil Society) publicly accessible.</p> <p>KPI: Website live and stable with no critical errors; all modules accessible.</p> <p>KPI: Fixes made to any broken or outdated links and media.</p> <p>Month 3–4 Post-Project.</p> <p>Milestone: Basic post-launch maintenance completed, including minor technical updates and user experience checks.</p> <p>KPI: At least 1 partner-led user walkthrough or internal usability review conducted.</p> <p>KPI: Any user feedback from initial launch reviewed and addressed where possible.</p> <p>Month 4–5 Post-Project.</p> <p>Milestone: Targeted dissemination activities initiated within project partner networks.</p> <p>KPI: Training shared in at least 3 relevant policy, academic, or practitioner newsletters or platforms.</p> <p>KPI: At least 1 conference presentation or webinar includes SOOC showcase.</p> <p>Month 5–6 Post-Project.</p> <p>Milestone: Planning initiated for continued use and potential adaptation of the training in future project or institutional workstreams.</p> <p>KPI: At least 1 discussion or planning session on integration into future proposals or training offers.</p> <p>KPI: Summary of course usage data and early feedback compiled and reviewed.</p>
Costs	n.a.
Revenues	n.a.
Other sources of coverage	n.a.

Table 13. Exploitation Intention Table of Key Exploitable Result 2 (KER2): Toolkit on biodiversity for educators (D5.10 Adjusted training materials for secondary and higher education).

<p>Description</p>	<p>The educational materials will be tailored for both secondary and higher education curricula with some materials adjusted to primary education, as well as other extra-curricula educational settings. The materials will be available in at least four languages (e.g. English, French, Romanian, Hungarian, Portuguese) and will be disseminated EU-wide among formal and non-formal education professionals, organisations and networks. The educational materials will consist of an online course for educators, and lesson plans adjusted to the target audience (secondary or higher education, with some materials adjusted to primary education).</p> <p>The training materials focus on biodiversity, systems thinking, biodiversity’s interaction with the food and fashion systems, and the benefits of interacting with nature.</p>
<p>Target market/ end users</p>	<p>Target market:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Schools (mainly secondary but also primary education) and higher education professionals, organisations and networks • Non-formal education professionals, organisations and networks <p>Customers/end-users:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teaching professionals in primary, secondary and higher education • Non-formal educators - civil society organisations involved in education across many domains, informal educators outside schools – e.g., scouts, guides
<p>Competitive advantages</p>	<p>By the current practice in many European countries, environmental education is often delivered in a siloed way, mainly within the context of scientific subjects, which results in a disconnect from the socio-economic and emotional aspects of environmental topics. There tends to be a lack of progression from primary to secondary schools. Many teachers lack the training to approach environmental topics with their students, as well as the time to dive into these complex topics (in the classroom and in terms of preparation time). PLANET4B offers users well-developed, flexible educational materials for secondary and higher education with some materials adapted to primary education, translated in multiple languages, that can be easily and flexibly adapted to everyday teaching practice.</p> <p>To respond to the need for teaching materials available in local languages, the training materials will be available in at least 4 languages, therefore they will be accessible worldwide, and easily adaptable for other languages.</p>

	<p>To respond to the need for flexible, modular materials that can be linked to the school curricula, the educational materials will be broken down into modules.</p> <p>To respond to the need for educational materials on environmental topics that bring stimulating, interdisciplinary perspectives to students, the training materials will include innovative perspectives and creative methods.</p> <p>To respond to the lack of training and time for many teachers to learn about environmental topics, whilst some of their students are knowledgeable at young ages on environmental topics, the materials will include 'off-the-shelf' lesson plans for busy teachers, as well as an online course for educators which will allow them to feel confident about teaching the lesson plans.</p>
Use model	<p>Service: The lesson plans as part of the adjusted training materials will be flexible and ready-to-use tools for educators in high and secondary schools (with some materials adjusted to primary education) as well as non-formal educational settings, e.g. outdoor schooling. Before delivering the lessons, teachers can take the online course to feel more confident about teaching the lessons, which will contribute to teachers' professional development. The online training platform will be provided by PLANET4B partners.</p> <p>Early adopters: Project partners and their networks</p> <p>School networks</p>
Partners	<p>Lead partners: TEHRA (previously CAC) will lead with secondary schools, one university for higher education (Radboud University potentially, Coventry University to support), ESSRG for primary education</p> <p>Contributor partners: Coventry University, Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg, ESSRG, IFZ, University of Pisa, CzechGlobe, Radboud University</p>
Timing	2025
IP status	<p>Creative Commons license (e.g. CC0 or CC-BY) will be applied. The license will be carefully selected, taking into consideration Intellectual Property Rights.</p>

Table 14. Exploitation Roadmap of Key Exploitable Result 2 (KER2): Toolkit on biodiversity for educators (D5.10 Adjusted training materials for secondary and higher education).

Actions	Actions (3–6 months after project end)
	<p>M1–M6: Design and implement an outreach plan including:</p> <p>Lead: TEHRA (previously CAC), support from all partners</p> <p>Launch webinar to present the toolkit to educators, stakeholders, educational policymakers. We will invite early adopters and partners to present use cases.</p> <p>Social media promotion: Schedule and make posts across platforms such as LinkedIn and Instagram. Focus especially on educator groups and environmental communities. Partner networks will help amplify reach.</p> <p>Workshops: Facilitate both online and in-person workshops (where possible) to introduce the toolkit to educators.</p> <p>Planned workshops: 1 workshop for educators in Brussels, October 2025; 2 workshops for educators in Romania, Nov. 2025; 1 workshop in France, Nov. 2025.</p> <p>Promotion of the toolkit at environmental education events such as the EC’s Education for Climate Day.</p> <p>M2–M4: Map out alignment of the toolkit’s learning objectives with the EU’s GreenComp competence framework and explore certification pathways for educators.</p> <p>Lead: TEHRA (previously CAC)</p> <p>Conduct a mapping of the toolkit content and learning objectives to the EU GreenComp competence framework ("systems thinking", "fostering collective action").</p> <p>One option (TBC): issuing a paper-based certificate for those completing both the online course and a post-training survey, as a way to encourage feedback.</p> <p>M1–M6: Explore collaborations with educational networks and platforms.</p> <p>Lead: TEHRA (previously CAC)</p> <p>Outreach to networks: Establish and strengthen links with networks such as eTwinning, European SchoolNET, EPALE to host and distribute the toolkit.</p> <p>New partnerships: Leverage the partnership with the new HE project on museum education for SDGs to expand reach into the cultural education sector.</p> <p>Formal and informal actors: Initiate pilot collaborations with eco-schools, scout associations, and teacher training institutes.</p>

	<p>M1 – M3: Develop educator feedback loops (surveys) to refine materials post-project.</p> <p>Lead: TEHRA (previously CAC), support from CU</p> <p>Usage tracking: Monitor downloads</p> <p>Learning outcome evaluation: Design pre- and post-training self-assessment tools for educators to assess skill/knowledge gain and satisfaction.</p> <p>Implement means for users to send feedback.</p> <p>M1 – M6: Identify and pursue further funding like national funding, Erasmus+.</p>
Roles	<p>Main responsible: TEHRA (secondary education focus), with support from Radboud University and Coventry University for higher education and ESSRG for primary education.</p> <p>Technical maintenance of platform: Coventry University</p> <p>Dissemination and network engagement: All partners</p>
Milestones	<p>Online course launched: 25 registered users (M6), 50 downloads (M6)</p> <p>Outreach plan implemented: 1 launch webinar, 2 participations in EU-wide education events, 15 social media posts, dissemination through 5 communication channels (M6)</p> <p>Satisfaction survey (M5): e.g., 80% positive feedback (KPI)</p> <p>Certification for educators: 25 certificates delivered (M6)</p> <p>Training, workshops delivered by TEHRA/CAC team: 5 (M6)</p>
Costs	<p>Outreach – 1 year: €5000; 3 years: €10000 (staff costs)</p> <p>Certification – 1 year: €1000; 3 years: €2000 (staff costs)</p> <p>Training, workshops – 1 year: €5000 (staff costs) and €2000 (travel costs); 3 years: €12000 (staff costs) and €5000 (travel costs)</p> <p>Keeping the content and the translations up-to-date - 1 year: €5000; 3 years: €10000 (staff costs)</p> <p>TOTAL YEAR 1: 18,000 EUR</p> <p>TOTAL YEAR 3: 39,000 EUR</p>
Revenues	<p>It is very difficult to estimate revenues as schools have very small budgets so licensing hinders uptake of materials in general as well as inclusion of schools beyond private schools. We can expect donations for 1 year: €500–1000. Revenue can also arise as speaking at events fees and consultancy fees at €500–1000 for 1 year.</p>
Other sources of coverage	<p>New EU grants (Erasmus+, Horizon Europe follow-ups): adapt the training for other types of educators, join other research-focused</p>

	<p>projects to further develop the training (new translations would be involved).</p> <p>Partners' own institutional budgets where possible (The Climate Academy, universities).</p> <p>New national education funding.</p> <p>In-kind support through volunteer and partner educator network.</p>
--	--

Table 15. Exploitation Intention Table of Key Exploitable Result 3 (KER3): 3 Comprehensive guidelines tailored for enabling players (D5.8).

Description	Three practical guidelines for each target group (civil society, policymakers and businesses) to provide detail on potential transformative pathways, intersectionality context, behaviour and creative methods, and communication tips on biodiversity.
Target market/ end users	The target market is NGOs and civil society, policymakers, and business looking to engage their audiences and/or employees in pro-biodiversity thinking, decisions and actions.
Competitive advantages	A lot of biodiversity messaging and engagement is not user specific. While the overall aim is the same, by tailoring messages to specific groups with specific needs/pressures, our guidelines will be more useful to various groups and this holistic approach should bring greater advantages for biodiversity than a one-size-fits-all approach.
Use model	Service: The guidelines will be made available to support policymakers, businesses, and NGOs who wish to prioritise biodiversity, or engage the public on biodiversity priorities. These guidelines will overlap with the training materials in D5.9 (KER1) that are specifically tailored to the target groups and teach engagement methods and learnings from their application within different intersectional contexts in PLANET4B. The guidelines will also signpost users to relevant reports from the project. Early adopters will be those businesses, policymakers and NGOs that have been engaged in PLANET4B for market research for the training resources and within other contexts e.g., UNEP-WCMC
Partners	Coventry University
Timing	2025
IP status	Creative Commons license (e.g. CC0 or CC-BY) will be applied. The license will be carefully selected, taking into consideration Intellectual Property Rights.

Table 16. Exploitation Roadmap of Key Exploitable Result 3 (KER3): 3 Comprehensive guidelines tailored for enabling players (D5.8).

Actions	The guidelines will be available on the Care-full Courses website (D5.9 and D5.10) by the end of October where they will sit alongside the engagement interventions and the transformative change stories. Any promotion of the site and its materials will automatically include the guidelines. More detail around the promotion can be found in D5.9 roadmap.
Roles	CU and TEHRA (previously CAC) will lead on exploitation of the website and its resources via social media and existing networks (e.g. Human Behaviour Change Newsletter, Access Newsletter, as well as sharing it with those organisations used for market research to develop the materials in the first place). UNEP-WCMC can connect with their networks of policymakers and businesses.
Milestones	Website shared in at least three newsletters of lead exploitation partners.
Costs	n.a.
Revenues	The Care-Full Courses website is free to access. There will be no revenues.
Other sources of coverage	Partners' own institutional budgets covered by Horizon Europe DAISY and additional institutional budgets.

Table 17. Exploitation Intention Table of Key Exploitable Result 4 (KER4): Catalogue of transformative intervention methods (D2.4 Catalogue of transformative intervention methods for various enabling players).

Description	<p>A practical and science-based catalogue of intervention methods that facilitate intrapersonal, interpersonal, and institutional change. The methods – ranging from experiential learning games to arts-based and deliberative approaches – support biodiversity prioritisation in decision-making by enabling social learning and behavioural change.</p> <p>The catalogue includes for instance, Pathbreak: A Biodiversity-Food-Governance Game, Biodiversity in my cupboard, night walk and participatory theatre along with guidance and concrete cases how to use these methods across diverse social, ecological, and cultural contexts.</p>
Target market/ end users	Biodiversity-focused decision-making across Europe (and beyond), including environmental governance, education, NGOs, and private sector sustainability practice also facilitators of workshops and participatory processes in biodiversity-related contexts.
Competitive advantages	Integrates behavioural science, intersectionality, environmental justice and biodiversity – a missing combination of current toolkits. Co-developed and tested with real-world case studies across Europe Includes a diverse mix of experiential, creative, and

	deliberative methods tailored to different levels of learning and change (intrapersonal, interpersonal, institutional). Specifically aligned with social learning theory and transformational leverage points, not only awareness raising, backed by empirical testing, such as games tested with students, learning communities, and civil society actors. It enables both digital and physical participation, allowing different forms of engagement, while provides a variety of methods tailored for different contexts and audiences.
Use model	Provision of a service: as a toolkit in participatory processes, policy interventions, and community-based biodiversity actions, educational purposes. Training: accompanying workshops and sessions for WP3 & WP4 implementers (already planned within the project lifecycle). Integration into capacity-building, policy recommendations, and other WP outputs.
Partners	Lead partner: Coventry University (CU); Other partners involved: MLU, WCMC, ESSRG, IFZ, NINA, RU, UNIPI, FiBL,
Timing	2025
IP status	Content to be shared via Creative Commons licensing for educational and policy use. Open-access with attribution (aligned with Horizon Europe open science principles); published through PLANET4B channels, deliverables, briefs and Zenodo.

Table 18. Exploitation Roadmap of Key Exploitable Result 4 (KER4): Catalogue of transformative intervention methods (D2.4 Catalogue of transformative intervention methods for various enabling players).

Actions	Finalisation of dissemination and exploitation materials: production of a polished, user-friendly open-access catalogue (PDF/online interactive version, Zenodo publication, project website hosting). Training and capacity-building offer: updated development of a training package (slides, facilitation manuals, exercises) to accompany the catalogue, tailored to different audiences (policy, NGOs, educators). Promotion and outreach: targeted communication to policymakers, civil society, businesses, and researchers through newsletters, EU science-policy platforms, policy briefs, and conference presentations. Partnership building: establish synergies with sister projects (BioAgora, BioTrails, BioNEXT, etc.), EU clusters, and relevant networks (Alternet, IPBES, CBD).
Roles	Coventry University (CU) – lead on scientific quality and long-term hosting of outputs, integration into future projects, e.g. using the materials in the Horizon Europe, DAISY. MLU – mainly responsible for exploitation roadmap, lead on training provision and integration into capacity-building.

	Other PLANET4B partners – academic exploitation through integration into teaching curricula and further EU/national research projects.
Milestones	M2 (Month +3): Catalogue of methods further promoted among 100 stakeholders, extended training package available. M3 (Month +6): First external uptake in a non-PLANET4B context (e.g. workshop with policymakers or NGOs). M4 (Year +1): Integration into at least 2 professional training programmes.
Costs	Staff time for training delivery, outreach, and catalogue updates (~€15k) Communication and dissemination materials (~€5k) Participation in key policy/science events to promote the catalogue (~€5k) Integrated into DAISY and other project activities of CU, ESSRG and MLU.
Revenues	N/A
Other sources of coverage	Partners' own institutional budgets covered by Horizon Europe DAISY and additional institutional budgets.

10.4 Additional dissemination and exploitation activities

Beyond the Key Exploitable Results, the project has generated a number of valuable outcomes over its three-year duration. Disseminating these results and making the accumulated knowledge useful will remain an important task for the consortium members even after the project's completion.

The lessons learned from the case studies, maintaining the personal and professional networks established within the Learning Communities (LCs) and Advisory Boards (ABs), and sharing the content of research reports with the scientific community, as well as with business and civil sectors, not only requires considerable effort but also provides a solid foundation for future projects, local initiatives, new research, effective advocacy, and professional collaborations.

The dissemination plans of the project partners were assessed through a short questionnaire.

Due to the nature of the partnership, the primary dissemination tools are future scientific publications (7 mentions) and presenting the project's results at conferences (6 mentions).

Based on the results, three actors committed (IFZ, FUG, UNIPI) to preparing policy recommendations in the future, while IFZ also planned to present findings at policy meetings.

A straightforward and direct way of exploiting the results is their integration into future research or practice-oriented projects. Nine partners referred to this possibility, and several such projects have already been launched or are in development – for example, DAISY, Healthy and Biodiverse Edible Cities, and Community Park in Graz (based on the experiences of WomenGarden).

The project outcomes are also being utilised by incorporating creative methods developed within PLANET4B – such as Pathbreak (simulation game, Biodiversity-Food-Governance game), the Systems Mapping Workshop structure, and the Learning Community as a form of participation – into the organisations' own working methods, workflow, and future projects. This applies particularly to practice-oriented partners (CGE, FUG, TEHRA, and DADIMA's).

Publishing reports and results on thematic online scientific platforms is an effective way to reach a wide audience for PLANET4B. Among such platforms, Zenodo and ResearchGate are the most popular and are preferred by most partners, though thematic platforms such as Education for Climate (the EC's platform on environmental education) and the New European Bauhaus newsletter are also used. At the same time, the Horizon Booster Platform (HRP) has great potential, though it is less well-known, which is why we are actively promoting it among the partners.

Most project partners engage in some form of educational or training activity. The results of PLANET4B can be directly applied in these contexts, as 80% of the partners indicated that they integrate the knowledge gained (e.g. lessons from case studies, teaching materials, learning resources, research reports) into their future educational and training practices.

It is also worth highlighting that, as a result of the project, two new creative, education-focused online platforms have been created, providing long-term access to information for visitors: the teaching materials at Care-full Courses & Resources (a Key Exploitable Result), and the Pathbreak game available at pathbreak.eu.

11. Monitoring results

In order to achieve the successful implementation of CDE activities and fulfilment of the relevant objectives and KPIs (Table 19), a systematic monitoring has been carried out throughout the project implementation. The monitoring is performed internally on an annual basis and officially reported in the relevant deliverables. Regular monitoring allows the identification of possible risks and deviations from the CDE objectives and performance indicators and the timely planning of any necessary corrections and actions to address potential implementation problems. Such an approach improves the overall performance of the relevant activities and enable a more efficient evaluation.

An online form has been created for reporting all CDE activities PPs are performing. The form is available on SharePoint/Teams to all PPs. Specific CDE and WP5 relevant templates are created for monitoring purposes and were sent out to request data on a six-month basis until the final reporting from all PPs.

Online presence of PLANET4B has been monitored using specific analytics monitoring software, i.e. Google Analytics as well as relevant social media analytics (number, age, source, distribution, location of the visitors on website, number of posts, followers of the project's social media profiles or views of YouTube videos).

Table 19. Key Performance Indicators*.

Tools	KPI	Target	Current results (October 2025)
Website	No. of visitors	5.000	6000–6500 (estimated)
Newsletter	No. of subscribers	200	200
Social media	No. of followers	1.000	1050
	No. of posts	700	705
Videos, illustrations and artwork	No. of videos produced	10	25
	No. of target groups reached	500	1300 views of videos (plus additional outreach through dissemination)
Infographics	No. of infographics	5	5
	No. of target groups reached	500	n.a.
Press release	No. of press releases sent	5	4 on project level (plus 9 released by PPs)
Non-scientific articles (e.g. The Conversation), radio and TV interviews	No. of articles	30	48 on the external channels plus 40 on the website
	No. of radio interviews	5	4 (2 FIBL podcasts, 2 ESSRG)
	No. of TV interviews, spots	2	n.a.
	No. of people reached	100 000	71 223
Scientific publications	No. of publications	5	7
Workshops for enabling players and stakeholders	No. of workshops organised	64	63
	No. of participants	200	412**
Consultations	No. of consultations	10	29
Joint actions with other EU projects (e.g. joint event, joint communication)	No. of actions	10	26
Presentations at scientific conferences and events	No. of presentations	5	72
Public deliverables	No. of deliverables	28	29
Deliverable briefs (a creative, short version of the main messages)	No. of briefs	25	20
Online training	No. of online trainings	1	4 (exploitation and dissemination)

	No. of target group participants	300	is planned after M36)
	No. of education institutes/youth groups reached	100	

* Total number of target audience reached (documented) from all communication, dissemination and exploitation activities.

** As some of the workshops and events overlapped with other categories, such as conferences and events, the actual number of participants is substantially greater, but at least 412 have been reported in the workshops category.